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БІОПАЛИВ

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF THE ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF THE NEW DIETARY SUPPLEMENT “AS-AN”

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Abstract: This article discusses the results of studies conducted in vitro to determine the antioxidant activity of the new food additive “As-AN” by inhibiting the autoxidation reaction.

Keywords: Helicobacter pylori, antioxidant, “As-AN”, quercetin, gliclazide, flavonoid.

Introduction. Nowadays, the demand for medicinal products derived from healing plants is increasing day by day. The growing need for medicinal plants and the necessity to meet this demand require the discovery of lesser-known plant species and the development of new types of biologically active compounds, medicinal products, and dietary supplements based on the study of their chemical composition and biological activity.

The *Plantago major* plant, belonging to the Plantaginaceae family, is used in traditional medicine to treat more than 80 different diseases. This plant possesses high regenerative properties and has been used since ancient times for the treatment

of both internal and external wounds.

Free radicals cause more than a hundred diseases in humans, including atherosclerosis, arthritis, tissue ischemia and reperfusion injury, central nervous system damage, gastritis, cancer, and Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS). Antioxidants are essential for neutralizing free radicals. They react with free radicals in biological systems, reduce the damage caused by them, and protect against their indirect effects.

Antioxidants (also known as anti-oxidizers or preservatives) are substances that inhibit oxidation. They include numerous chemical compounds that neutralize the oxidative effects of free radicals and other agents. These substances may be naturally produced by the body or obtained through food.

Kobesay and his colleagues studied the antioxidant activity of *Plantago major* by preparing extracts from its leaves and seeds using hot water, cold water, and ethanol. The antioxidant activity of each extract was determined in vitro using the stable radical 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH). The results showed that the ethanolic extract of plantain leaves exhibited the highest antioxidant activity (78%) even at low concentrations. In contrast, the ethanolic extract of the seeds demonstrated significantly lower activity (25%) at similar concentrations. Experiments also confirmed that both hot and cold aqueous extracts of the leaves exhibited higher antioxidant activity compared to those obtained from the seeds.

Experimental Section. The objective of our study was to investigate the antioxidant properties of the “As-AN” preparation. To this end, the antioxidant activity of “As-AN” was assessed through phytochemical analysis. The antioxidant activity of the samples was determined by measuring the inhibition of adrenaline autoxidation in vitro, which helps to prevent the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). The method is based on the inhibition of the adrenaline autoxidation reaction, and the percentage of inhibition (%) reflects the capacity of the preparation to block the formation of active oxygen species over time under in vitro conditions.

The antioxidant activity of aqueous extracts of “As-AN” was analyzed using UV-Vis spectrophotometric analysis with a Cary 60 UV-Vis spectrophotometer from

Agilent Technologies. In order to study the biological activity and healing properties of “As-AN,” the aqueous extracts were used to prepare analytical solutions at concentrations of 10%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% by diluting the initial stock solutions with bidistilled water (see Table 1).

Table 1

Preparations Prepared from “As-AN” Extracts

№	Remedy	Solubility	<i>In vitro</i> mkg/ml
1	“Ac-AN”	water	100/250/500/750/1000

For the analysis, 2.0 ml of 0.2 M sodium carbonate buffer (Na₂CO₃–NaHCO₃, pH = 10.65) and 56 µl of 0.18% adrenaline (epinephrine) hydrochloride solution were used. 30 µl of antioxidant preparations were added, and measurements were taken using a Cary 60 UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Agilent Technologies) at a wavelength of 347 nm, at intervals ranging from 30 seconds to 10 minutes.

A solution with a concentration of 1 mg/ml was used as the standard for comparison. As the control, 2.0 ml of 0.2 M buffer and 56 µl (5.46 mM) of 0.18% adrenaline were used.

The antioxidant activity was calculated based on the inhibition of adrenaline autoxidation using the following formula:

$$AA\% = \frac{D_1 - D_2 \times 100}{D_1}$$

Here

- **AA** – Antioxidant activity of the tested solution, expressed as a percentage (%);
- **D₁** – Optical density of the solution containing buffer and adrenaline hydrochloride;
- **D₂** – Optical density of the solution containing the tested extract and adrenaline hydrochloride.

The results of the calculations are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.**Spectrophotometric and Antioxidant Activity (AA%) Indicators of “As-AN”****Extracts**

№	“Solutions under analysis”.	Control D₁	Experiment D₂	AA %
1	(10%) 100 mg/ml	0.1894	0.1636	13.65
2	(25%) 250 mg/ml	0.2100	0.1784	15.02
3	(50%) 500 mg/ml	0.2451	0.2026	17.34
4	(75%) 750 mg/ml	0.2669	0.2171	18.67
5	(100%) 1000 mg/ml	0.3397	0.2743	19.24
	Gliclazide			10,03%
	Quercetin			36,94%

To perform a comparative analysis of the antioxidant activity of the test samples, two reference substances were used: Gliclazide (C₁₅H₂₁N₃O₃S) – a pharmaceutical compound known for its antioxidant properties and widely used in medicine – and Quercetin (C₁₅H₁₀O₇) – a biologically active compound commonly used as a dietary supplement in the food industry.

To evaluate the activity of the plant-derived preparations, five different concentrations were prepared: 100, 250, 500, 750, and 1000 µg/ml. The study began with the screening of these concentrations.

The antioxidant activity of the preparations was assessed using the adrenaline autoxidation method under in vitro conditions. Phytochemical analysis of the tested preparations was carried out to evaluate their antioxidant potential. The antioxidant capacity was determined based on the inhibition of adrenaline autoxidation, which prevents the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS).

The antioxidant activity of the test preparations was compared to that of standard antioxidants quercetin and gliclazide. The results confirmed the presence of antioxidant properties in the tested extracts.

The strong antioxidant activity of the preparation is attributed to the presence of polyphenolic compounds, particularly flavonoids such as:

1. Luteolin

2. Apigenin
3. Baicalin
4. Hispidulin as well as organic acids like:
5. Ursolic acid
6. Ferulic acid
7. Oleanolic acid

These compounds are known for their ability to neutralize carcinoma cells. In addition, *Plantago major* extracts have demonstrated cytotoxic effects against breast adenocarcinoma and melanoma cells, which may be attributed to the presence of the flavonoid luteolin-7-O-beta-glucoside (8).

The antioxidant compounds present in the “As-AN” dietary supplement, prepared from *Plantago major*, including polyphenols and water-soluble vitamins, contribute to the healing of various wounds.

It is advisable to conduct comprehensive scientific research on the chemical composition and pharmacological properties of this medicinal dietary supplement.

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